

IMPROVING THE DYNAMIC MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES AT INTERMEDIATE STRAIN RATES

Sanghyun Yoo¹, Giuseppe Catalanotti², Nathalie Toso¹, Yves Toso¹, and Heinz Voggenreiter¹

¹ Institute of Structures and Design, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Stuttgart, Germany,

² Advanced Composites Research Group (ACRG), School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Queen's University Belfast, Belfast, UK

Introduction

Motivations

- Reliable experimental data at intermediate strain rates are essential to generate the material cards for the numerical tools used in crashworthiness design and to predict the crash behaviour of vehicles by simulation.
- Dynamic tests are inherently difficult due to the dynamic interaction between test specimen and test machine.

Objectives

- To investigate a newly developed slack adapter and its associated test protocol for a servo-hydraulic high-rate testing machine able to reduce inertial effect-induced oscillations in force signals.
- To assess strain rate dependence of carbon/epoxy composites (Hexply® IM7/8552) at intermediate strain rates.

Methodology

Results

Dynamic stress-strain data of $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens for **in-plane shear properties** at different strain rates **without** (solid lines '-'), and **with damping materials** (dot lines '-.-').

Dynamic stress-strain data of 90° specimens for **transverse tension properties** at different strain rates **without** (solid lines '-'), and **with damping materials** (dot lines '-.-').

Conclusions and Outlook

- Dynamic material properties of carbon/epoxy composites at intermediate strain rates up to 200 s⁻¹ are identified.
- Test procedures are improved with the newly developed slack adapter and an adhesive bond clamping method.
- The use of damping material is crucial to obtain reliable dynamic properties.
- The in-plane shear tests show a clear rate-dependent behaviour with increasing strain rates.
- Although a trend on strain rate dependence of transverse tension properties can be captured, the transverse tensile strength from this study is approximately 33% lower compared to published results.

Acknowledgements

H2020-MSCA-ITN-2016
No 721256

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 721256.